

PUBLIC EXPENDITURE AND ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA (2000-2019)

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Abstract

The study aimed at determining the relationship between public expenditure and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria (2000-2019). The study was guided by three objectives, three research questions and three research hypotheses. The study employed the exploratory and ex-post facto designs. The exploratory design guided the collection of data from text books, journals, articles, and other relevant materials for hypotheses formulation, while the ex-post facto design was used because the events under study had already taken place and cannot be controlled. The population of the study consisted of public expenditure in the selected ministries of Akwa Ibom State Government from 2000- 2019. The sample of the study consisted of public expenditure from 2000- 2019. Purposive sampling technique was used. The instrument used was the audited budget from the Office of the Auditor General of Akwa Ibom State from 2000-2019. The instrument was face validated by experts in the Accounting and Measurement and Evaluation, Faculty of Education, University of Uyo Nigeria. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Split half reliability test to analysed the public expenditure from 2005- 2011. The split half reliability is a statistical method used to measure the internal consistency of the scores of a test. The reliability estimates were as follows: Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sufficiency = .905, Ministry of Education = .888 and Ministry of Health = .991. The data was time series data collected using the desk survey approach from approved recurrent and capital estimates of Akwa Ibom State and Report of the Auditor-General on the Accounts of Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria from 2000 to 2019. Simple linear regression was used for data analysis for the research questions and for testing the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there was significant relationship between public expenditure on education; health; and agriculture; works and economic performance of Akwa Ibom State. Based on the findings it was recommended amongst others that government of Akwa Ibom State

should increase the budget of educational sector to 30% of the total budget and ensure full implementation to foster research and development.

Keywords: Economic Performance, Government Expenditure, GDP, Education.

1 Introduction

The goal of every economy is to maintain a high level of employment, stabilize prices, promote rapid growth of gross national product, maintain a favourable balance of payments position, promote a free market economy, satisfy collective demands, redistribute income equitably, promote infant industries, encourage the priority sector and balance population development and promote labour and capital development. These explain why the expenditure of governments the world over has maintained a consistent upward trend. This continuous increase in the volume of public expenditure is targeted at expanding the functions of government through the direct investment in industrial innovations, public health, education, commercial activities, etc with a view to achieving growth. According to Arrow and Kurz (2010), public expenditure is the most powerful economic factor of all modern societies. The form and pattern of the output growth of any economy is determined by the structure and size of its public expenditure.

Akwa Ibom State public expenditure structure can be segmented into recurrent expenditure and capital expenditure. The components of the recurrent expenditure include expenditure on administration (interest on loans and maintenance, salaries and wages) while capital expenditure captures government projects on the generation of the electricity, education, telecommunication, airports, roads, and so on. The provision of public infrastructural facilities has been one of the fundamental bases for public expenditure. Providing and maintaining these infrastructural amenities cost a huge amount financing. Hence, investment on infrastructures and productive activities spending is expected to positively contribute to the growth of the economy whereas spending on consumption by the government retard growth. It is argued that the country will benefit socially and economically from government investment (spending) on health, education, agriculture, works etc. Among the world of scholars, the issue of impact of public expenditure on the growth of the economy has sponsored continuous debate.

Governments have been found to be involved in two basic functions, that is, the protection functions (security) and the provision function. Government protection functions include the establishment of the rule of law and property rights enforcement. With thin function, the security of lives and properties are offered, the criminality risk is minimized, and the country is secured from external aggression. The provision functions centres on the provision of public goods and services to include agriculture, works, health and education. For instance, the expenditure of

government on education and health engenders labour productivity and increases national output growth. Similarly, infrastructural expenditure on power, roads, communication, etc. reduces the costs of production, facilitates the development of the private sector and industrial profitability, hence, fostering the growth of the economy (Nurudeen and Usman, 2010). The enormous effects of public expenditure on economic growth have continued to attract attention of the economists recently. However, public expenditure allocation without due consideration to the rising needs of the economy is bound to bring about huge distortions in the economy which may retard growth. Government has concerned since the 1960 to allocate public expenditure continuously into the different economic sector in the economy. According to Olabisi and Funlayo (2012), the basic determinant for this allocation has been by political consideration instead of concise economic considerations.

Ordinarily, public expenditure leads to the reduction in poverty level, standard of living improvement for the citizens, equality in the distribution of income, the overall wellbeing improvement and the growth of the economy. Government engages a number of policy measures as economic interventions which include market failure bailout or social equity improvement via resources redistribution. And the only government can embark on these intervention measures successfully is through expenditure. Often, expenditure most time is more advantageous than various policy measures like loans and guarantees, regulations and tax expenditure. Particularly, expend time of government appears to be somewhat transparent, making the government accountable to the country over their decision. For instance, the sustainability, distribution and burden of regulation can be easily determined due to the difficulty in measuring the economic effects.

Expenditure as an expression of gross domestic product (GDP) is regarded as the measure of the direct involvement of government in the entire economic activity. Expressing expenditure as a proportion of GDP is beneficial in two ways at least. Firstly, it made available the basis for comparing spending analysis overtime. Expenditure as a proportion of GDP unlike the nominal dollars provides the basis of comparing meaningfully, the relative use of resources between years. Finally, it further revealed relatively, the degree/extent of the intervention by government in the economy and also aid in social choice analysis (Akpan, 2005).

Public expenditure refers to the purchase of goods and services, which include public consumption and public investment, transfer payments consisting of income transfers (pensions, social benefits) and capital transfer and its performance is usually assessed in terms of the achievement of economic activities. These objectives can be long term, such as sustainable growth and development, or short term, such as the stabilization of the economy in response to sudden and unpredictable events.

Furthermore, its performance can be measured in three key variables (Gross Domestic Product, Human Development Index and Inflation Rate) that indicate whether the economy is growing, or in recession. Like many other indicators, income, output, and spending can also be measured in per capita (per head) terms. Per capita gross domestic product (GDP) is a metric that breaks down the country's GDP per person. It is calculated by dividing GDP over a country's population. Gross domestic product per capita income is a universal measure for gauging the prosperity of the nations. Worldwide, it is used by economists alongside GDP to analyse the prosperity of a country and its economic growth.

Thus, public expenditure has become an important factor for self-sustaining productivity improvements and long-term growth. Sustained and equitable economic growth is clearly a predominant objective of public of public expenditure in all sectors of the economy. It is therefore incumbent on government to allocate public spending across various sectors of the economy in order to maximize the prospects of achieving its growth and developmental objectives for better performance of the economy.

The researcher observed that government budget in Akwa Ibom State on education in 2018 stood at N10.52b, health N8.21b, road construction N211.423b, and industries N6.800b, while in tourism, the budget rose to N14.604b. In 2019, the budget for education stood at N15.050b, health N18.021b. This means that education and health have not been given priority in government schedule. The budget showed that low expenditure in the educational sector is adversely affecting the quality of government free and compulsory education going on in the state. Increasing expenditure on education will go a long way to support free and compulsory education and positively impact the economic performance of the state. In the health sector, the researcher observed that when drugs are prescribed to patients, most patients, are advised to purchase it outside the hospital stand. The roads construction in Akwa Ibom State is giving the government very serious challenges because of the abandonment of majority of these road projects. Budgeted figure of N157.311b in 2019 indicated that not much has been achieved on road projects as most of the roads are not in good shape. These observations warrant the researcher to find out the extent to which public expenditure relates with economic performance in the chosen area of the study.

Education is considered a major remedy for many problems faced by developing countries and the importance of government expenditure in the process of human development (education) is well recognized. Improving the education of people is not only a goal in itself for a better quality of life but also its positive impact on the economic development of a country is far-reaching (Yogish, 2006). Odior (2011)

reported that investing in education is one of the pro-growth policies for promoting economic growth. Oriakhi and Ameh (2014) reported that increased funding to education reduced corruption; increase teacher's motivation and strategic planning among others and the sector will be appreciably developed. The provision of education is a key element of a policy to promote broad-based economic growth. Education plays a great and significant role in the economy of a nation, thus educational expenditures are found to constitute a form of investment. This augments individual's human capital and leads to greater output for society and enhanced earnings for the individual worker. It increases their chances of employment in the labour market, and allows them to reap pecuniary and non-pecuniary returns and gives them opportunities for job mobility. Education is a source of economic growth and development only if it is anti-traditional to the extent that it liberates, stimulates and informs the individual and teaches individuals how and why to make demands up. The budget on education is less than the 26% of the total budget figure required by UNESCO. The same is applicable in health sector.

Government spending on health plays a crucial role in economic growth. Therefore, the healthier nature of population determined their ability to contribute to economic performance. Babatude (2012) asserted that better health enables better earning ability for both workers and enterprises which in turn enhance the tax base of the government leading to better fiscal posture. These interactions, all things being equal, will lead to better economic performance. Thus the manner in which growth is shared also influence the rate of poverty reduction. Health is one of the significant factors that determine the quality of human capital which is a necessary factor for economic growth. Based on this paradigm developing countries have attempted to enhance the human capital through public health expenditure as well as government spending on education and other social services. Imoughele and Ismaila (2013) reported that health enhances worker effectiveness and the productivity of an individual through increase in physical and mental capacities which are necessary for economic growth and development. Al-Yesufy (2000) and Lawson (2009) noted that education, health care, training and investment in social services enhances and improves the human capacity which has a spillover effect on economic growth. However, the state of health and the level of infrastructure have hampered productivity in the health sector. This affects the agricultural sector.

Agriculture is an important sector of Nigerian economy in the world today. Agricultural sector acts as catalyst that accelerates the pace of structural transformation and diversification of the economy, enabling the country to fully utilize its factor endowment, depending less on foreign supply of agricultural product or raw materials for its economic growth. Apart from laying solid foundation for the economy, it also serves as import sector, as it provides readymade market for raw

materials and intermediate goods for industries. However, Government expenditure is referred to as outflow of resources from government to other sectors of the economy (Nurudeen & Usman 2010). Government spending or public spending is sub-divided into current and capital expenditure. Capital expenditure has been defined as payment for non-financial assets used in production while current expenditures are payments for non-repayable transactions within a year, (CBN, 2003). Agriculture is the bedrock of economic growth, development and poverty eradication in the developing countries. Agriculture has also regarded as the engine and panacea to economic prosperity (Sertoğlu, 2017). The battle for long-term economic growth will be won or lost in the agricultural sector.

In view of the importance of public expenditures in the transformation of an economy, it is imperative for the state government to spend more on human and capital development. The researcher is of the opinion that more expenditure be allotted to some important sectors like education, health, agriculture and industries which can foster greater development. Government needs to curtail expenditure in some sectors that do not propel fast development of the state. It is also evident that increase in public expenditure has yielded the desired growth and/or improve the economic performance in the state. It is on this basis that the researcher intends to investigate the extent of relationship between public expenditure and economic performance of Akwa Ibom State.

Statement of the Problem

The huge expenditure profile of the government over the years is sufficient enough to boost productivity in all sectors and facilitate growth. Government spends substantial resources in both human and material resources with the aim of improving the nation's infrastructural facilities, boosting social welfare and empowerment packages for the masses, employment generation, as well as creating enabling environment to facilitate the growth of private investment. In spite of this, growth in the State seems to be more of a story than reality.

Thus, government expenditure has become an important factor for self-sustaining productivity improvements and long-term growth. Sustained and equitable economic growth is clearly a predominant objective of government expenditure in all sectors of the economy. It is therefore incumbent on government to allocate public spending across various sectors of an economy in order to maximize prospects of achieving its growth and development objectives for better performance of the economy.

Education plays a great and significant role in the economy of a nation, thus educational expenditures are found to constitute a form of investment. The education

system is undeniably the major backbone of the development of any country as it inculcates in the individual, the ability to be a vital part in nation building. Education enriches peoples understanding of themselves and the world; it improves quality of lives and leads to broad social benefits to individuals and society. Education raises people's productivity, creativity and promotes entrepreneurship and technological advancement.

In Nigeria, the decline in the standard of education at all levels has become a fact of national life. Indeed, the most significant event in the sector in the recent past has been the continuing crisis besetting the sector. This crisis is rooted in the degenerating conditions within the citadels of learning, with respect to teaching facilities and other infrastructural facilities, the welfare of those engaged in the teaching profession and the ever increasing cost of education. This has culminated in student unrest and industrial actions by lecturers and teachers through their respective umbrella associations such as Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT) and so on at their different levels of the educational system. Much of the difficulty lies in the fact that the sector is poorly funded. These results in shortages of materials and human resources for education: lack of qualified teachers, a brain drain for the public sector; few institutional inputs, shortage of classrooms and a host of other problems.

Several of the issues in the financing of education in Nigeria are embedded in virtually endemic problems of fiscal federalism – in particular, the so called vertical and horizontal fiscal imbalances. The first of these deals with the imbalance between financial responsibilities and financial resources at each level of government, federal, state and local. The second deals with equity across the subunits of each specific level of government such as state, or local government.

Health sector has clearly showed its role in influencing economic performance, at least at the micro level. It is suggested that, all things being equals, healthier workers are more likely to be able to work longer, be generally more productive than their relatively less healthy counterparts, thus able to secure higher earnings than diseases ridden workers. Babatude (2012) posited that poor health infrastructure, illness and diseased shorting the working lives of people thereby reducing their life time earnings. However, Alabi, Adams, Chime, Abu and Aiglomudu (2010) reveal that in Nigeria less than 1% of GDP was allocated to health care provision, and about 2% of government oil revenue was allocated to health sector in Nigeria between 1981 and 2006. The fact that this low financial commitment will result in inequality in access to health care resources and since majority of Nigerian are poor and pay for their health care out of their pocket money may be left of health care provision. Nigerian project Agenda (2007) has shown that accessibility to health care facilities in Nigeria is low.

It was revealed that only 3 out of 5 Nigerians have access to health care facilities. A critical look into the share of public expenditure on health in the national budget revealed that the share of health is rather low. The percentage of public health expenditure on total government expenditure according to world health organization in 1995, 2000, 2005, and 2010 was 7.05%, 4.22%, 6.41% and 4.4% respectively. This suggests that Nigerian health care situation still needs some improvement in budget allocation mostly in the area of planning and execution.

Agriculture is the bedrock of economic growth, development and poverty eradication in the developing countries. Agriculture has also regarded as the engine and panacea to economic prosperity. Nigerian economy in past decades strives on the agricultural sector. The sector is reputed as the mainstay of the economy in the early 1960's. It is seen as the key driver for growth and development. In most developing countries (low and middle-income countries), the agricultural sector remains, the largest contributor providing inputs, food, employment opportunities, raw materials for other industries, provision of foreign earnings from exportation of the surpluses, and more importantly the enormous advantage of the value added in the various production process (Izuchukwu, 2011).

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between public expenditure and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, this study seeks to determine the relationship between:

1. public expenditure on education and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State.
2. public expenditure on health and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State.
3. public expenditure on agriculture and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

The following research questions will be raised to guide the study.

1. What is the relationship between public expenditure on education and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State?
2. What is the relationship between public expenditure on health and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State?
3. What is the relationship between public expenditure on agriculture and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will be formulated and tested at .05 level of significance.

- H01: There is no significant relationship between public expenditure on education and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State.
- H02: There is no significant relationship between public expenditure on health and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State.
- H03: There is no relationship between public expenditure on agriculture and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State

2 METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study

The study employed the exploratory and ex-post facto designs. The exploratory design guided the collection of data from text books, journals, articles, and other relevant materials for hypotheses formulation, while the ex-post facto design was used because the events under study had already taken place and cannot be controlled (Udoka and Anyingang, 2014). The study predominantly used secondary source of data. The data were time series data collected using the desk survey approach from text books, journals, internet, CBN statistical bulletin and other relevant government publications. The study covers the period from 2000 to 2019.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of public expenditure in the selected ministries of Akwa Ibom State Government from 2000- 2019.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample of the study consisted of public expenditure from 2000- 2019. Purposive sampling technique was used.

Instrumentation

The instrument used was the audited budget from the Office of the Auditor General of Akwa Ibom State from 2000-2019. The audit reports are statutory documents of the State Government.

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was face validated by experts in the Accounting and Measurement and Evaluation, Faculty of Education, University of Uyo Nigeria.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was determined using Split half reliability test to analysed the public expenditure from 2005- 2011. The split half reliability is a statistical method used to measure the internal consistency of the scores of a test. The method involves splitting a test into halves and correlating examinee's scores on the two halve of the test. The reliability estimates were as follows: Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sufficiency = .905, Ministry of

Education = .888, Ministry of Health = .991, Ministry of Industry and Tourism = .674 and Ministry of Works = .997. This high coefficient value indicated that the instrument is reliable for the study as recommended by Uzoagulu (2011); that the coefficient value of 0.60 and above is considered reliable for survey studies. The computation is attached as Appendix II.

Method of Data Collection

The data was time series data collected using the desk survey approach from text books, journals, internet, CBN statistical bulletin and other relevant government publications. The study covers the period from 2000 to 2019.

Method of Data Analysis

Simple linear regression was used for data analysis for the research questions and for testing the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance.

3 RESULTS

The results of the analysis were presented in Tables.

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between public expenditure on education and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 1: R and R² of the Relationship between Public Expenditure on Education and Economic Performance in Akwa Ibom State

Variables	R	R-square	Adjusted square	R-	Std. Error
Expenditure on Education	.851 ^a	.724	.708		782602467.23983
Economic Performance					

Source: Office of Auditor, Akwa Ibom State, 2021

The result presented in Table 1 reveals a correlated coefficient R-value of .851 which shows the relationship between public expenditure on education and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State. The table further shows the coefficient of determination (R²) value as .724. The (R²) value of .724 which is the strength of association which implies that 72.4 percent of public expenditure on education was executed and that was the level of performance.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between public expenditure on health and economic

performance in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 2: R and R² of the Relationship between Public Expenditure on Health and Economic Performance in Akwa Ibom State

Variables	R	R-square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error
Expenditure on Health	.980 ^a	.960	.958	389492205.41789

Economic Performance

Source: Office of Auditor, Akwa Ibom State, 2021

The result presented in Table 2 reveals a correlated coefficient R-value of .980 which shows the relationship between public expenditure on health and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State. The table further shows the coefficient of determination (R²) value as .960. The (R²) value of .960 which is the strength of association implies that 96 percent of public expenditure on health was executed and that was the level of performance.

Research Question 3

What is the relationship between public expenditure on agriculture and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 3: R and R² of the Relationship between Public Expenditure on Agriculture and Economic Performance in Akwa Ibom State

Variables	R	R-square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error
Expenditure on Agriculture	.825 ^a	.681	.662	167302679.63355

Economic Performance

Source: Office of Auditor, Akwa Ibom State, 2021

The result presented in Table 4.3 reveals a correlated coefficient R-value of .835 which shows the relationship between public expenditure on agriculture and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State. The table further shows the coefficient of determination (R²) value as .681. The (R²) value of .681 which is the strength of association implies that 68.1 percent of public expenditure on agriculture was executed and that was the level of performance.

Research Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between public expenditure on education and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4: Result of Simple Linear Regression Analysis of the relationship between Public Expenditure on Education and Economic Performance in Akwa Ibom State

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Regression	2736425532652997 0000.000	1	273642553265299700 00.000	44.679	.000 ^b
Residual	1041193256940764 4000.000	17	612466621729861380. 000		
Total	3777618789593761 0000.000	18			

Source: Office of Auditor, Akwa Ibom State, 2021; **significant at P= .05;

a. Dependent Variable: Economic Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Public Expenditure

The result in Table 4 shows that the computed F-value as 44.679 with 1 and 17 degrees of freedom as well as the p-value of .000. Since the p-value is less than ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between public expenditure on education and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State is rejected, while the alternative is retained. Hence, it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between public expenditure on education and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between public expenditure on health and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 5: Result of Simple Linear Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Public Expenditure on Health and Economic Performance in Akwa Ibom State

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Regression	619010360027514600 00.000	1	61901036002751460 000.000	408.038	.000 ^b
Residual	257897102738189880 0.000	17	15170417808128816 0.000		
Total	644800070301333600 00.000	18			

Source: Office of Auditor, Akwa Ibom State, 2021; **significant at P= .05

a. Dependent Variable: VAR00006

b. Predictors: (Constant), VAR00005

The result in Table 5 shows that the computed F-value as 408.038 with 1 and 17 degrees of freedom as well as the p-value of .000. Since the p-value is less than ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between

public expenditure on health and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State is rejected, while the alternative is retained. Hence, it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between public expenditure on health and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State.

HO₃: There is no relationship between public expenditure on agriculture and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 6: Result of Simple Linear Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Public Expenditure on Agriculture and Economic Performance in Akwa Ibom State

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	101418913816592 0900.000	1	1014189138165 920900.000	36.234	.000 ^b
Residual	475833172413604 220.000	17	2799018661256 4956.000		
Total	149002231057952 5120.000	18			

Source: Source: Office of Auditor, Akwa Ibom State, 2021, **significant at P= .05

a. Dependent Variable: Economic Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Public Expenditure on Agriculture

The result in Table 6 shows that the computed F-value as 36.234 with 1 and 17 degrees of freedom as well as the p-value of .000. Since the p-value is less than ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between public expenditure on agriculture and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State is rejected, while the alternative is retained. Hence, it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between public expenditure on agriculture and economic performance in Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study have been organized and discussed according to the five research questions raised and the five hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The research questions were discussed first followed by the hypotheses as outlined below.

Public Expenditure on Education and Economic Performance

The finding of research question one revealed that public expenditure on education has a very strong relationship with economic performance of Akwa Ibom State. The

hypothesis one indicated that there is a significant relationship between public expenditure on education and economic performance of Akwa Ibom State. This necessitates the rejection of the null hypothesis and the retention of the alternate hypothesis. The finding is supported by the report of Odior (2011) who conducted a study on “Government Spending on Education, Economic Growth and Long Waves in a CGE Micro-Simulation Analysis: The Case of Nigeria.” The result shows that the re-allocation of government expenditure to education sector is significant in explaining economic growth in Nigeria. The finding also is in consonance with the report of Oriakhi and Ameh (2014) who conducted a study on “Government Expenditure and the Development of the Education Sector in Nigeria: An Evaluation”. The use of co-integration in this work shows there is a long-run relationship between the variables and they are statistically significant. The Granger Causality test shows that the various variables granger causes literacy rate in Nigeria. The researchers posited that increased funding reduced corruption, teacher’s motivation and strategic planning among others if fully implemented; the sector will be appreciably developed. Yogish (2006) opined that education as an investment secures returns in the form of skilled manpower that geared to the needs of development, both for accelerating economic development and for improving the quality of the society.

Public Expenditure on Health and Economic Performance

The finding of research question two revealed that public expenditure on health has a very strong relationship with economic performance of Akwa Ibom State. The hypothesis two indicated that there is a significant relationship between public expenditure on health and economic performance of Akwa Ibom State. This necessitates the rejection of the null hypothesis and the retention of the alternate hypothesis. The findings of this study is supported by the report of Imoughele and Ismaila (2013) who conducted a study on “Determinants of Public Health Care Expenditure in Nigeria: An Error Correction Mechanism Approach.” the results show that demand for health in Nigeria is price inelastic. It also shows that that total population of 14 years of Age and younger and health expenditure share in gross domestic product (proxy for government developmental policy on health) are the major determinants of health expenditure in Nigeria while gross domestic product per capital, unemployment rate, population per physician, consumer price index and political instability are insignificant. The finding also aligned with the view of Babatude (2012) who postulated that good health has positive impact on the learning ability of children which lead to better educational outcome, school completion rate, higher means of years schooling, achievement and increases the efficiency of human capital formation by individuals and households. The finding is supported by the view of Lawanson (2009) who asserted that health is one of the major components of human capital formation, while Todaro (2007) revealed that human resources

constitute the ultimate basic for the wealth of a nations, capital and natural resources are passive factors of production, human beings are the active agents who accumulate capital, exploit natural resources, build social economic and political organization and carry forwards national development.

The finding is supported by the report of Agbatogun and Taiwo (2010) who empirically examine the determinants of health expenditure in Nigeria. The researchers show that improvement in health sector is sine-qua-non to sustainable economic growth and development. The authors found that gross domestic product is the most important determinants of health allocation and literacy rate and population's growth rate are insignificant determinant of health expenditure in Nigeria. The researchers recommended that there is need for health sectors reformed in order to improve the health of the people and reduce the burden on the government by encouraging more private sector participation. The finding is supported by the report of Omotor (2009) who carried out same study in the Nigeria's economy for the period of 1970-2003 using co-integration analysis. His main findings are that health expenditure in Nigeria is income inelastic and public financing for health expenditure appears to have more impact on health expenditure than other determinants including per capital income.

Public Expenditure on Agriculture and Economic Performance

The finding of research question three revealed that public expenditure on agriculture has a very strong relationship with economic performance of Akwa Ibom State. The hypothesis three indicated that there is a significant relationship between public expenditure on agriculture and economic performance of Akwa Ibom State. This necessitates the rejection of the null hypothesis and the retention of the alternate hypothesis.

The finding is in consonance with the view of Olawumi and Oyewole (2018) conducted a study on "Public Expenditure on Agriculture and Output Growth in Nigeria." The study empirically evaluated the nexus between public spending on agriculture and Nigerian output growth. The study employed secondary data, the data which spanned from 1981 through 2016. The findings show that agricultural development in Nigeria has positive impact on the economic growth in Nigeria and that all the variables in the model proved significant, which shows that agricultural sector output has positively impact on the economic growth in Nigeria over the period under study. The finding also aligned with the view of Sertoğlu (2017) who opined that agriculture is the bedrock of economic growth, development and poverty eradication in the developing countries. Agriculture has also regarded as the engine and panacea to economic prosperity.

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